

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Prevalence of Occupational Hazards among Hospital Cleaners at the University of Maiduguri Teachings Hospital (UMTH).

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Abstract

The hospital cleaning job is outsourced to companies that employ unskilled cleaners. Despite being an important role, little attention is paid to the workplace hazards the hospital cleaners are exposed to. This study assessed the knowledge, attitude, perception and prevalence of occupational hazards among hospital cleaners in UMTH. A 30-item questionnaire was used as a primary tool in which the questions related to the knowledge; attitude, perception and prevalence were asked. 200 such questionnaires were administered to various hospital cleaners through a random sampling method using a cross-sectional descriptive study. Data collected were summarized and analyzed with IBM-SPSS statistics version 20 software. The study was conducted over eight weeks. Most of the respondents 199 (99.5%) were aware of the hazards associated with their occupations and all the respondents 200 (100%) were aware of safety measures. About 133 (56.5%) of the respondents have not had injuries in the last one year. All the respondents 200 (100%) practice hand washing after work and had a training program before employment, physical hazards is the most recognized with 180(90%), while ergonomically hazard is the least recognized with 36(18%). Needle stick was the highest recognized injury with some 153 (76.5%), while blood splash was least affected only 77(38.5%). In conclusion, the management of the confer company, as well as the UMTH to adequately neutralize work-related hazards in the hospital, recommend adequate provision of safety kits, their timely

replacement when worn-out and updated job aides should be made available to all hospital cleaners. The management of the confer company should provide grip boots and adequate gloves to hospital cleaners. Media such as televisions and radios should be used to inform the public on issues related to occupational hazards and safety. The management of the confer company and UMTH should improve their Salary scale.

Keywords: Occupational, Hazard, Hospital, UMTH, Cleaners.

1. INTRODUCTION

Occupational health is defined by the Joint Committee of the International Labor Organization Committee and the World Health Organization (WHO) as “ the promotion and maintenance of the highest degree of physical mental and social well-being of workers in all occupations; the prevention among workers from departures from health caused by their working conditions; the placing and maintenance of the worker in occupational employment adapted to his physiological equipment and to summarize: the adaptation of work to man and of each man to his job. While occupational injury is defined as a work, material substance, process or situation that predisposes to disease or an accident to workers in the workplace and even years after the workers have left the workplace, the cleaning work in most tertiary health facilities in Nigeria is contracted to cleaning companies which in turn employ the cleaner to execute the work. In the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH), the confer cleaners are employed to clean the hospital. Outsourcing non-clinical services in the hospital is used in the developed countries as well.

Hospital cleaners routinely clean patient rooms, nursing units, surgical areas, and public restrooms. They clean furniture, polish floors and vacuum carpets, empty trash, restock medicine supplies, collect dirty laundry from all patient areas and distribute the clean lining and hospital gowns.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Though the cleaners are unskilled, they play vital roles in cleaning hospitals' interiors and premises. Cleaners though exposed to various hazards in health facilities, work with poor safety practices and inappropriate safety tools. They are often employed with little or no knowledge of occupational safety and risks involved in handling biohazard wastes and other body fluids in health facilities. They are therefore

vulnerable to diseases such as Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Lassa Virus, Ebola Virus and other blood-borne pathogens that can be transmitted via body fluids and excrements (nosocomial infection). They are also vulnerable to back and neck pain, burnt-out stress, allergic reactions to latex materials, spills from chemicals, radiation exposure, and assaults from patients. Basic preventive measures to avoid health challenges are often neglected. These include education and training of employed hospital cleaners, it is of concern to observe that people work in these poor safety conditions and often they are under pressure, low pay and no insurance coverage or welfare packages. They must know how to protect themselves from potentially infectious wastes.

1.2 Aims and objectives

The aim of the study is to assess the knowledge, attitude and prevalence of occupational hazards among hospital cleaners at the university of Maiduguri teachings hospital. The aim of this research can be achieved through the following objectives:

- (a) Determine the hazards associated with hospital cleaning;
- (b) Assess the cleaners attitudes/safety measures towards; and determine the prevalence of occupational hazards in UMTH;
- (c) Identify the challenges faced by hospital cleaners in performing their duties;
- (d) Assess the frequency of training/workshops/programs in UMTH for old and new recruited cleaners; and
- (e) Proffer recommendations.

Research Questions

- (1) What are the hazards associated with hospital cleaning?
- (2) What are the rates of occupational hazards prevalence?
- (3) What are the challenges faced by the hospital cleaners?
- (4) What is the frequency of training/workshops/programs?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Occupational health became a major health problem during the period of the Industrial Revolution when it started as just prevention of accidents in factories and mills, but now has advanced to embrace all employments and other disciplines like

ergonomics and occupational psychology. Similarly, various legislations have been put forth by government agencies concerned with labour and productivity. These legislations include safety laws, workman's compensation laws, and environmental laws. Workers unions and associations also have one of the major goals to protect the health and safety of their members, e.g. the International Labor Organization (ILO) and Nigerian Labour Congress (NLC).

Knowledge of occupational hazards among cleaners in healthcare facilities is required for them to be able to properly handle potentially hazardous hospital wastes and reduce the spread of infections within and outside healthcare centers. Lack of knowledge occupational hazards among hospital cleaners go hand in hand with avoidable disease burden in society.

The findings of a study carried out in Ondo Nigeria, showed that hospital cleaners with more than ten years of experience had better awareness of occupational health safety (OHS). As it is in the sanitary and cleaning industry worldwide, most of the local hospital cleaners are females who are on average older than those employed in other trades. Qualification-wise, the majority of hospital cleaners have only basic academic qualifications. Some of them have no formal education at all. However, prudence in the workplace is mostly exhibited by cleaners who are relatively more educated.

Another study carried out by Anozie et al in south-east Nigeria found that a fairly significant proportion of cleaners who participated in the survey were aware of their HIV, Hepatitis B and C virus status but only half of them were immunized for HBV as well as had knowledge of post-exposure prophylaxis for HIV.

The attitude of hospital cleaners concerning occupational hazards cannot be overemphasized. Hospital cleaners' attitudes in their workplace go hand in hand with the quality of work they do. Negative attitudes of cleaners may be triggered by poor working circumstances like, poor leadership and management, shortage of cleaners, overcrowded wards, poor communication and uncooperative behaviors among healthcare workers. A study done in Kampala, Uganda by Raw Lance, revealed that using all necessary personal protective equipment is associated with reduced exposure to both biological and non-biological hazards. Working overtime increases the likelihood of experiencing both biological and non-biological hazards

3. METHODOLOGY

The study is a cross-sectional descriptive one to assess the knowledge, attitude and perception of occupational hazards among hospital cleaners in UMTH, Borno State. The respondents are hospital cleaners (confer cleaners). This method was chosen because it ensured a wider coverage and representation of all hospitals clean in UMTH. The tool for the study is a questionnaire.

A simple random sampling method was used to select 200 cleaners; both male and female cleaners from among the cleaners in the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital on the days of the survey. The sample consists of 400 confers cleaners. Respondents were first lightened about the importance of the study and questionnaires administered by the researcher afterwards. Every eligible respondent was selected except for those who did not consent to the study until the sample size was obtained. The primary source of data was through the administration of a design questionnaire in the English language. It comprises open and semi-structured questions. The questionnaire was designed to include the topic of research, introduction and sections A, B and C. Two hundred questionnaires were generated based on the objective of the study.

Section A: consists of Bio Data (age, sex, occupation, tribe, religion, marital status, academic qualification. Duration of service, monthly salary, tobacco/alcohol intake)

Section B: is designed to assess the occupational hazards exposed by the hospital cleaners, such as physical, biological, chemical, psychological and ergonomically.

Section C: is designed to assess the level of awareness and practice of health safety measures by answering the questions on, Awareness of safety measures Use of protective devices Training on safety measures

The questionnaires were filled by the researchers during cleaners' shifts and also at the cleaners' convenience. All relevant information obtained from the respondents through the questionnaire was analyzed using IMB-SPSS software (version 20). A percentage of various aspects were determined and relevant inferences were made. Data is presented using tables; chi-square is used to determine associations.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 200 questionnaires were produced and administered among cleaners. The results obtained were summarized, analyzed and presented in tables of frequencies as shown below:

OBJECTIVE 1: KNOWLEDGE OF OCCUPATIONAL HAZARDS ASSOCIATED WITH HOSPITAL CLEANING AMONG CLEANERS IN UMTH.

Research Questions 1: Hazard Awareness.

Table 1: Hazard Awareness

Hazard Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	199	99.5
No	1.00	0.50
Total	200	100

(Source: Field survey 2017)

From table 1 above it shows that 199 (99.5%) of the respondents are aware of the hazards associated with their occupations. This does not correspond to the study done by Haifete (24) which showed that only 50 per cent of the cleaners were aware which could be because it is a study on waste segregation, not occupational hazards. Studies on general health care workers such as the study done by Aluko et al (23) and Osunbemi et al (10) showed that most respondents were knowledgeable about hazards in health care facilities with 89 and 84.6 percent respectively.

Objective 2: Assessments of the cleaners attitudes/safety measures towards; and determines the prevalence of occupational hazards in UMTH

Research Question I: Hazard Types and Prevalence

Table 2: Hazard types and awareness

Hazard Type	Frequency	Percentage
Needle Stick Injury	56	32.2
Musculoskeletal	28	16.1
Slip/fall	46	26.4
Chemical splash	32	18.4
Others	54	16.9
Total	200	100

(Source: Field survey, 2017)

Table 2 above shows the type of injury sustained by cleaners in UMTH in the last year. It shows that out of 200 respondents that sustained different forms of injuries, needle stick is the injury ranking highest as the most sustained injury affecting 28 (32.3%) respondents. this does not correspond to a study done by Alamgir and Yu (26) which shows that musculoskeletal injuries were the most prevalent nature of injury for cleaners representing 59 percent of all injuries and punctures were In only 6 percent. Ilesmi et al (13) revealed that out of the 200 respondents, 182 (79.1%) had chemical injuries carrying the highest percentage. This study is higher than our study here in UMTH. This could be probably due to differences in study location and the knowledge of the risk of infection.

Research Question II: CLEANERS ATTITUDES TOWARDS THEIR OCCUPATIONAL HAZARDS IN UMTH.

(1) Protective Devices

(2) Wearing of protective glove

(3) Hand Washing after work

(4) Frequency of Hand Washing by cleaners

The charts above indicate that all the respondents (200) wash their hands after work. The frequency of hand washing was 200 (100%) respondents, 85.5% washing regularly wash their hands and 11.5% wash their hands from time to time. This is similar to a study done by Ndejjo et al (14) which revealed that most (79.5%) health workers washed their hands before and after every procedure, 68.5% after handling soiled materials, 46% when their hands were dirty while slightly over half (53.5%) did so after using the toilet. 79% of the respondents don't feel like wearing protective devices, while 17.1% use it only when is available while 3.5% claimed that the protective devices are not provided.

Research question 3: Safety Measures’.

Table 3: Safety measures

Safety Measures	Frequency	Percentage
Facemasks	195	98.5
Gloves	199	99.5
Goggles	22	11.5
Safety Boot	187	91
Apron	25	12.5

Concerning the safety measures in table 3 above, out of the 200 respondents it shows that 98.5% wear face masks, 99.5% wear gloves, 11.5% wear Goggles, 91% of the respondent wear safety boots and 12.5% of the respondents wear Apron. The most used form of safety measure is the face mask with about (98.5%) respondents and 99.5% wearing gloves. This is similar to a study done by Aluko et al (23), which revealed that wearing hand gloves and facemasks for clinical procedures was practiced by most respondents (96.2%). The high response was probably because gloves are the most widely recognized form of protection against cross-infection and contamination

(5) Awareness of safety Measures

The chart above shows that all the respondents 200 (100%) are aware of safety measures to protect them from hazards which was similar to a study done by Anozie et al (14) which reported that 960(100%) respondents among 10 hospitals were aware

of the safety measure to protect themselves from the hazards. This similarity is probably because the hospital cleaners received training before their employment. This is in contrast to the study done by Bamidele et al (25) which showed that 88.9 per cent of the respondents know of the hazards associated with their work.

Objectives 3: Challenges and Hazards Faced By Hospital Cleaners In hospital.

Table 4: Challenges and Hazards.

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Monthly income 5-10 thousand	200	100

Types of hazards exposed to		
Physical	180	90
Biological	115	57.5
Chemical	119	59.5
Psychological	114	57
Ergonomic	36	18
Sources of injuries		
Needle stick	153	76.5
Blood	77	38.5
Slip/fall	145	72
Chemical slash/inhalation	101	50
Cut		
Provider of protective device		
Hospital	1	0.9
Confer company	113	99.1
Confer company	114	100
Total	3	1.5
Replacement of safety device		
Weekly	11	5.5
Monthly	6	3
Yearly	178	89
On request	2	1
Not regular	200	100
Total		

Table 4 shows that all their salaries fall between the ranges of 5-10 which most respondents complained is low. It is similar to the study of Anozie et al (11) where 4 out of 5 respondents complained that their income is low. It also shows that the majority of them 180 (90%) were exposed to physical hazards. It does not correspond to the study done by Anozie et al (11) where half of the respondents were exposed to physical, mechanical and biological hazards. It is also not similar to the study done by Ndejjo R. et al (14) which revealed that the hazards were 39.5 per cent biological.

The table also shows that the injury with the highest prevalence is needle stick 153(76.5%). It is different from the study done by Bamidele et al (25) which shows the highest percentage of cuts and bruises (66%); Table 6 also shows that 99.1% of the protection devices are been provided by the cleaning company. This differs from the study done by Ndejjo R. et al (14) where 53.5% of health facilities provide health workers with personal protective equipment.

Finally, the table shows that the replacement of safety devices was responded to mostly based on request 178(89%).

Objective 4: Training Programs for Employed Cleaners In hospital

Table 5: Training programs in the hospital

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Training when employed		
Yes	200	100
Total	200	100

Table 5 shows that 200(100%) of the respondents had training for 1 month as against a study done by Anozie et al (11) which reported that only 64.7% had received some form of training on occupational hazards and safety. Also, a study done by M Sulaiman et al (21) reported that 67.4% of experienced cleaners had training. This is in keeping with the level of knowledge of occupational hazards and safety awareness of the hospital cleaners in UMTH.

ASSOCIATION OF SEX AND PREVALENCE AND SOURCES OF INJURY, PRACTICE, AMONG CLEANERS IN UMTH, MARCH-APRIL, 2017

ASSOCIATION OF SEX AND PREVALENCE						
	MALE	FEMALE	χ^2	df	P-VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
Injury in the last year	35	52	0.195	1	0.659	NO

ASSOCIATION OF SEX AND INJURY SUSTAINED						
Needle Prick	60	91	0.63	1	0.43	NO
Blood	29	48	0.37	1	0.847	NO
Slip/fall	60	84	2.178	1	0.140	NO
Chemical	42	58	1.035	1	0.309	NO
splash/inhalation	49	76	0.069	1	0.793	NO
Cut						

ASSOCIATION OF SEX AND PRACTICE OF PROTECTIVE MEASURES						
Wearing of protective device	34(44%)	74(60.2%)	3.815	1	0.05	YES
Hand washing after work	77	122	0.629	1	0.428	NO
	77	122	0.629	1	0.428	NO
	15	8	7.835	1	0.005	YES
Safety measures	72	110	0.960	1	0.327	NO
Gloves	11	14	0.365	1	0.546	NO
Goggles	75	121	0.024	1	0.853	NO
Safety boot						
Apron						
Face mask						

Table 6 shows the association of sex and the prevalence of injury sustained, the association is not significant ($X^2 = 0.195$, $p=0.659$, $df= 1$). Table 8 also shows the association between sex and wearing of the protective device, the association is significant, which was analyzed using chi-square ($X^2 = 3.851$, $p=0.05$ $df=1$). Similarly, there is a significant relationship between sex and wearing of goggles which were analyzed using chi-square ($X^2 = 3.851$, $p=0.005$ $df=1$). Other associations were not significant.

ASSOCIATION OF DURATION OF WORK AND INJURY SUSTAINED, PRACTICE AND PREVALENCE OF OCCUPATIONAL HAZARDS AMONG CLEANERS IN UMTH, MATCH- APRIL, 2017

ASSOCIATION OF DURATION OF WORK AND INJURY SUSTAINED							
	<5 YRS	5-10 YRS	>10 YRS	X^2	df	P-VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
Needle stick	68	49	34	3.869	2	0.145	NO
Blood	32	29	16	0.804	2	0.669	NO
Slip/fall	64	48	32	3.574	2	0.276	NO
Chemical splash/inhalation	36	39	25	2.217	2	0.330	NO
Cut	50	43	32	0.471	1	0.790	NO

ASSOCIATION OF WORK DURATION AND PREVALENCE INJURY IN THE LAST ONE YEAR							
	<5 YRS	5-10 YRS	>10 YRS	X ²	df	P-VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
Wearing of protective device							
Hand washing after work	82	69	48	1.866	2	0.390	NO
Safety measures							
Gloves	81	70	48	1.446	2	0.446	NO
Goggles	8	12	3	3.700	2	0.155	NO
Safety boot	72	62	48	6.273	2	0.043	YES
Apron	6	9	10	5.070	2	0.079	NO
Face mask	82	67	48	5.656	2	0.059	NO

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The cleaning work in most tertiary health facilities in Nigeria is contracted to cleaning companies which in turn employ the cleaners to execute the work. At the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) the confer cleaners are employed to clean the hospital. Outsourcing non-clinical services in the hospital is used in the developed countries as well.

It is always very important to note that, while he cleaners are needed for the cleaning of the health centres it is equally paramount to consider the safety of the cleaners. Going by the results of the research it is assumed that, the hospital has been doing very well, nonetheless, they need to do more in areas such as availability of safety device; most of all the enforcing of the practice.

Further to this, the highest form of hazards faced by the cleaners is that of needle stick and blood splash was the least, however, all the cleaners are aware of the safety measures at it should in the hospital. Protective devices are available to a reasonable consideration that explains as why some of the cleaners choose to use it when available and when it is not; fairly some of the cleaners has formed a habit out of this. In conclusion, the desired outcome of this research has shown to us that the probable methodology employed in conducting it has yield fairly the result as expected. The gaps created in the research are open to further criticisms and research.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above observation and conclusion the following recommendations were made;

1. The management of the confer company as well as the UMTH to adequately neutralize work-related hazards in the hospital.
2. Adequate provision of safety kits, their timely replacement when worn out and updated job aides should be made available to all hospital cleaners.
3. The management of the confer company should provide grip boots and adequate gloves to hospital cleaners.
4. Media such as televisions and radios should be used to inform the public on issues related to occupational hazards and safety.
5. The management of the confer company and UMTH should improve their salary scale.

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